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PEARL

Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells with Carbon Electrodes

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Executive Summary

The Deliverable 7.1 covers the communication and dissemination strategy for the PEARL project. It is a result from task T7.1 Dissemination and communication.

Timely and effective communication and dissemination of results are an essential part of every research and innovation project. This ensures that the gained knowledge or exploitable outcomes can benefit the whole society, and that any duplication of research and development activities is avoided.

This communication and dissemination strategy for the PEARL project has been developed as a preliminary plan to fulfil the aforementioned goals. This strategy will also ensure all possible communication and dissemination routes are identified and used throughout the course of the project. Additional routes will potentially be investigated and if found relevant will be integrated in the communication and dissemination road map at a later date.

It is vital that the communication and dissemination of the project's achievements should never jeopardize protected intellectual property (e.g. patent, product design) or further industrial application. In order to address this, before any activity (e.g. publication, presentation, etc.), strict rules of prior notice to all partners will be applied according to EC guidelines and the PEARL Consortium Agreement. Partners will have the opportunity to refuse dissemination of their own know-how (background or results) by others when it could potentially harm their interests.

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1. Introduction

To maximize project impact, effective dissemination, communication (and exploitation) activities are planned and executed. These activities foster targeted promotion of project results towards key target groups via tailored action assuring a committed participation and interest in the project by key stakeholders. Preliminarily identified target groups include e.g. market/industrial stakeholders, end users, financial actors, scientific community, policy makers and regulators including standardization bodies, civil society and public at large. The plan includes the development and deployment of a wide range of channels and tools, including quantitative and qualitative criteria for evaluating and measuring dissemination and communication success. All activities will highlight and acknowledge the financial support from the EU. PEARL will capitalize the networking potential of each partner involved to maximize the outreach of the project's dissemination and awareness raising activities and guarantee exploitation of results beyond the project duration. The exploitation plan itself will be given in Deliverable D7.2 – Exploitation Plan 1 due in project month 12 (30.09.2024).

Communication activities promote the project and its impact on stable high-performance Perovskite PV widely to all stakeholders throughout the lifespan of the project. PEARL will reach out to society to show the benefits of the project for citizens. A visual identity was created for the project to raise interest, to clarify the main messages and to increase awareness of the project and its outcomes. A social media strategy is developed to maximise dissemination of the results and to create public engagement and interaction. Specific communication targets include target number of publications and press releases as well as social media and website statistics.

2. Dissemination and communication rules

2.1. External Communication

In relation to the external communication, it has to be mentioned that the dissemination of the project’s achievements should never jeopardise the protection of generated intellectual property (e.g. patent, product design) or further industrial application. In order to address this, before any dissemination activity (publication, presentation) strict rules of prior notice to all partners will be applied, according to EC guidelines. Partners will have the opportunity to refuse dissemination of their own know-how (background or results) by others when it could potentially harm the partner’s interests. The Dissemination Manager in cooperation with the Exploitation and Innovation Manager will follow all the approval processes described above and will act as an internal executive approval body for any dissemination action organised by different partners.

All project outcomes will acknowledge the support of the European Commission as requested by Article 17 — COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND VISIBILITY of the EU Model Grant Agreements for the EU funding programmes 2021-2027 and follow its principles.

Prior notice of any planned publication should be given to other consortium members at least 45 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the consortium member proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit, the publication is permitted (Figure 1).

The following information shall always be stated in the publication: **“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101122283, project PEARL”**.

Figure 1: Information and timeline of intention of publication.

The procedures to allow all dissemination materials to be quality assured, including both the content and layout, are established with the aim of checking:

- messages transmitted outside of the consortium, including the suitability of the messages for the people addressed, emphasising the benefits and relevance for industry (when applicable)
- technical contents control in order to ensure the quality of achieved scientific and research objectives
- that scientific papers and publications contain sufficient reference to the project; and
- layout quality and overall suitability.

2.2. Guidelines for Partners

The European Commission is encouraging the Dissemination Leaders to record, track, monitor, coordinate and report all the project dissemination activities (publications, participation in events, contributions to press and media) within the Periodic Reports. An Excel file has been prepared in order to track each partner’s contribution, keep a complete list of possible future actions, and monitor/assess each dissemination activity. This file, created at the very beginning of the project, is composed of three different sheets: Scientific

publications, Events and Press & Media (Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4). The tables include information about each dissemination activity performed within the project (type and title, URL and references, targeted public and participants, date, location, PEARL partner responsible for such dissemination, visibility level, etc.) and associated methods (attendance, abstract submission, poster show, distribution of materials like fact sheet, newsletter, etc., oral presentations, DEMO/video show, stand/booth, press releases, post in social media, interviews and videos, etc.). It is distributed amongst the consortium members and updated internally every 6 months of the PEARL project duration. The updated information will be inserted in the official Periodic reports towards EC in M18 and M36.

Dissemination recording and plan								
Name of the journal/book	Publisher/editor	D.O.I. (*)	Title of the FF2S publication (#)	Partner responsible/main author	Authors	Cost of the Gold Open Access	Date of submission	Date of publication

Figure 2: Dissemination Recording – Scientific Publication.

Events															
Type of event (*)	Name of event	URL	Date	Place	Partner responsible/participants	Targeted audience (#)	Number of participants/visibility (C)	Outputs (i.e. n. of contacts taken - see sheet "contacts")	Dissemination activity						
									Attendance	Abstract submission	Paper submission	Poster submission	Lecture/Powerpoint presentation	Brochure/Newsletter distribution	Video/DEMO

Figure 3: Dissemination Recording – Events.

Press and Media											
Press and Media (*)	URL	Publication date	Partner responsible/a author	Targeted audience (#)	Language	Visibility (C)	Dissemination activity				
							Publication (press)	Web article	Web post	Visual contents	Interview

Figure 4: Dissemination Recording – Press and Media.

The following guidelines were provided to the partners as procedures for disseminating PEARL (i.e. submit a peer reviewed article, attend a conference, have a booth at a Trade Fair, publish press releases, post online information about the project, communicate with media, etc.):

- Send an email to the Dissemination Leader and to the other involved partners (i.e. coordinator and co-authors for publications) with basic information about the planned dissemination activities, respecting the clauses of prior to notice, approval and acknowledgement.
- The Dissemination Leader will update the Excel file that will be made available for partners on the shared MS Teams platform. Co-authorships in scientific publications are encouraged and possible joint participation of different PEARL partners at the same event will be coordinated by the Dissemination Leader.
- Once the article is published/ the conference or exhibition is closed/ the link to media channels is available, send to the Dissemination Leader by email some additional information for repository and update of the Excel.
- Every half year, the " PEARL recording dissemination" Excel file will be circulated by email amongst the project partners for a double check and updates.

The benefit of having periodic recording of the project Dissemination activities is to easily keep track of activities and to be able to provide regular and accurate updates to the EC.

2.3. Publication policy and Open science practices

All PEARL project partners are strongly committed to promote good open science research practices. The project coordinator, VTT, has signed the national Open science declaration and creates and commits to its own open science principles. VTT coordinates the project according to these policies and principles. Researchers in PEARL carry out and document research in a careful and considered manner. Researchers publish results and interpretations of their research in an open and transparent manner, and respect confidentiality of data or findings when legitimately required to do so. Collaborative way to work is a core element of research process and it is promoted within the consortium, and always followed in the targets and tasks of the project. Project specific dissemination practices are agreed on in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement signed by all beneficiaries.

Engagement with the society is important for creating more value by providing wider perspectives and input for the project's execution. This engagement is carried out in practice by active dissemination in social media, scientific journals and in webinars and conferences. All the scientific articles and conference papers produced are published primarily according to open access principles. and the Open Research Europe publishing platform is utilised when applicable.

Various research data and results will be collated and generated throughout the duration of the project. The main research results will be shared with the scientific community and general public through the World Wide Web. The emphasis of data management will be on faithful and reproducible record keeping, with an emphasis on transparency and accountability. The consortium has a preliminary plan with respect to managing products of research; data format and content; data access and sharing; re-use and redistribution; and archiving and preservation of access. This will be outlined in the Data Management Plan (Deliverable 1.3, due date 31.03.2024).

3. PEARL Dissemination and Communication Plan

PEARL dissemination actions transfer knowledge and project results to promote and enable the use and exploitation of project outcomes during and beyond the project lifetime. To ensure optimal timing and efficiency of the dissemination actions, this detailed initial dissemination and communication plan has been created.

3.1. Timeline

PEARL Dissemination plan foresees distinguishable phases of dissemination & communication activities during the course of the project as described below:

- Year 1 (M1 – M12):
 - set up of dissemination strategy
 - press release summarising the launch of the project
 - project website creation
 - first PEARL presentations at events
 - preparation of dissemination materials: factsheet, brochure, leaflet, roll-up etc.
- Year 2 (M13 – M24):
 - dissemination strategy implementation
 - continuous webpage update
 - clustering activities
 - scientific publications of the PEARL results
 - partners participating in conferences and symposia in related domains
 - preparation of dissemination materials: project booklet; poster/roll-up
 - press release summarizing the first half of the project
- Year 3 (M25 – M36):
 - dissemination strategy update
 - continuous webpage update
 - clustering activities
 - scientific publications of the PEARL results
 - partners participating in conferences and symposia in related domains
 - final public PEARL conference/event
 - final press release summarizing the whole project

3.2. Target audience

Various communication tools will be used and will be tailored to the needs of various stakeholders and audiences. The target audiences will include research community, broad public, industries and standards & regulation bodies. The identified channels and tools for the communication and dissemination are introduced in the following chapters.

Table 1. Plan for dissemination activities.

Expected results	Objective	Specific channels [quantity]
Market/industrial stakeholders		
Business models; products, technologies, LCA analysis; sustainability benefits; market and replication potential.	Generate interest among early adopters; cooperation; promote uptake of individual project results; foster sustainability in the sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 Professional fairs and events ○ 3 Stakeholder workshops ○ 5 Webinars ○ 2-5 Technical publications
Scientific community		
Research results; discussions and data generated by PEARL on innovative solutions for the production of PSC.	Contribute to scientific literature and state-of-the-art in relevant fields of research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ >25 Scientific publications ○ 1-2 Webinars ○ > 5 Theses/dissertations ○ Training and education
Policy makers		
Economic, environmental, performance compared to current alternatives, current regulatory barriers & policy recommendations.	Removal of barriers to uptake and spread of PSC and compliance of protocols with relevant standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1 Policy recommendations paper ○ 1 Policy conference ○ Horizon Results Platform ○ Contacts and meetings ○ Social media, e.g. LinkedIn
Standardisation bodies		
Technical characteristics/specifications.	Ensure compliance of PSC products, processes, and technologies with current standards, and/or feed the development of new and adapted standards.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Policy recommendations paper ○ Policy conference ○ Contacts and meetings
Civil society, NGOs, public, media		
Benefits and impact of the proposed solution; engaging stories and communication (understandable for non-specialists).	Raise awareness of PSC, and potential impact on sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ PEARL project video ○ Awareness raising campaign and active interaction in social media ○ Participation in citizen outreach events and the public discussion

Impact and success of dissemination activities will be carefully analyzed and assessed against pre-established key performance indicators (KPI's, see Table 2). Project Officer will be regularly informed about the communication outcomes and based on his decision EC communication channels could be used too.

Table 2: Key Performance Indicators for dissemination and communication activities.

Key Performance Indicator	Value	Description
Website – average monthly single users	≥ 200	# of users accessing the project website
YouTube video(s) – views	≥ 1500	# of views
LinkedIn – followers	≥ 200	# of professional followers
Networking events	≥ 15	# of events attended by >15 partners linked to existing initiatives
Press releases	≥ 200	# of media mentions
Newsletters	≥ 5	
Fairs	≥ 3	
Contributions to Scientific journals and conferences	≥ 25	# of papers

A role of a Dissemination Manager (WP7 Leader, Christian May, Fraunhofer) has been established in order to plan, follow, undertake, and monitor the planned communication and dissemination activities. Regular contact with all Work Package Leaders will ensure timely communication and dissemination of project outcomes and results.

3.3. PEARL logo

Proposals for the project logo were designed by Fraunhofer FEP and have been discussed with the partners. The following logo (Figure 5) was chosen as the best graphical representation of the project idea. The project logo is used in all the project related advertising materials including templates, website, leaflets, brochures etc.

Figure 5: PEARL logo in different versions.

3.4. PEARL project website

The PEARL project website (www.pearl-project.eu) has been set up in order to increase public awareness of the project and is available for both consortium members' and public access (Figure 6).

The website has been created in Open-Source software called WordPress. WordPress started as a blogging system but has evolved to be used as full content management system, that is completely customisable and can be used for almost anything within the field of web design. It allows fast and reliable customisation and has a user-friendly back-office environment which is a key for the website updates and file uploads.

The PEARL project website will ensure an on-going communication between the general public, experts, technicians etc. on one side and partners of the project on the other.

The website structure is composed of 6 main pages. The main navigation menu is placed at the top line of the webpage. At the beginning of the project, it includes the following sections: About, Project partners, Contact, Imprint. More sections (e.g. Project results) and subsections will follow during the project duration.

The website provides acknowledgement of EU funding as follows: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101122283, project PEARL.”

Figure 6: PEARL website main page.

The PEARL website will be actively maintained and updated during the entire project lifecycle.

The project will also be promoted through websites of PEARL partners (e.g. News sections, projects sections etc., see Figure 7).

The screenshot shows the ICIQ website page for the PEARL project. The page is titled "Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells with Carbon Electrodes". It features a navigation menu at the top with links for PUBLICATIONS, NEWS, CAREERS, STAFF, INTRANET, AGENDA, and social media icons. Below the navigation is a green header with "Research" and "Research Projects". The main content area is divided into a sidebar on the left and a main text area on the right. The sidebar lists various research-related categories. The main text area contains a detailed description of the project, its objectives, and key statistics. A small image of the European Union flag is also present, along with the text "European Collaborative Projects".

Figure 7: Information on PEARL on ICIQ website (https://www.iciq.org/research_project/flexible-perovskite-solar-cells-with-carbon-electrodes/).

3.5. PEARL dissemination materials

Several types of dissemination materials will be prepared during the course of the project in order to inform wide and various audiences on PEARL project and its development. They will be created and distributed widely in all key events.

3.5.1. Project factsheet

The factsheet will be prepared on the request of the EC in order to give basic information on the project including project description and project technical description and implementation. The objective of the information materials is to present the project in a short, simple, and easy to read way. It includes general project information, the project concept and expected aim. The material will also include information on the consortium members, contacts of the project coordinator and manager as well as a link to the project's webpage. The fact sheet can be distributed both electronically and in printed form by each partner during events and meetings with stakeholders.

3.5.2. Project folders and leaflets

Project folders and leaflets for large non-specialized scientific community and stakeholders will be created and distributed to partner's institutions, European Commission and on dissemination events. If possible, infographics will be used for better visualization of the information and project's objectives.

3.5.3. Press releases

The aim of the Press releases is to attract favourable media attention and provide publicity for the project and its events.

The first Press releases on the project's launch will be published beginning 2024 introducing its topic, objectives, challenges, and consortium partners. The Press release will be released in English versions as well as translated in the partners' languages (e.g. German, Finnish, Italian, Polish) to have a broader and local impact.

Additional press releases will be produced during the course of the project, and they might be connected with important results / milestones achieved. All press releases will be available on PEARL website and also distributed by individual partners through their companies' websites or their networks/newsletter.

3.5.4. Roll-up and posters

The project posters can have different objectives and targets: to catch the attention with visual contents during exhibitions and workshops with stakeholders (also stimulating questions and requests of more details) and/or provide technical details, showing the scientific results, in a short way, to scientists and experts during the conferences. In order to make the presentation of the PEARL project in different events a roll-up will be developed including the general project information, the description of the PEARL concept and approach with visual contents, the logos of partners and the webpage link. Other posters with scientific contents could be developed by the partners and presented during scientific symposia and conferences, showing the tangible results and data the achievements.

3.5.5. Newsletter

Newsletters (>5) will be prepared to disseminate key project achievements and will include among others: innovation results, presentations at conferences, announcements of workshops/other events, achievement interviews with key research.

3.5.6. Social Media

LinkedIn will be considered to enable feedback from various audiences. Posts about the PEARL project and its development would be shared on the identified tools especially during events, conferences, and symposiums. An example project LinkedIn post is shown in Figure 8.

Youtube will be used to publish at least one project video. Because of the changing effectiveness of X (formerly Twitter), this channel is no longer considered.

Figure 8: PEARL post in LinkedIn.

3.6. Publication of PEARL results

Publication of PEARL results to relevant scientific and industrial periodicals, journals and key conferences in Europe will be assured throughout the whole project lifetime.

3.6.1. Scientific articles in journals

Joint publications from different partners are encouraged during the course of the project. The main scientific results of the project will be published OPEN ACCESS in scientific journals.

Examples of journals, where contributions from PEARL partners might be expected (the list is not exhaustive):

- Flex and Print Electronics
- ACS Energy Lett.
- Adv. Mater.
- Adv. Energy. Mater.
- J. Am. Chem. Soc.
- J. of Power Sources
- Joule
- Nat. Energy
- Nat. Electronics
- Nat. Mater.
- Rev. Sci. Instr.

3.6.2. Project Presentation at conferences, symposia, meetings, fairs

A set of conferences, symposia and fairs on Photovoltaics and Flexible Electronics as well as manufacturing technologies has been identified by partners to disseminate PEARL results. During these events, the representatives of the project will have the possibility to communicate the project's scope and possible interaction and exchange with initiatives and projects in related fields.

Here are examples of events, where presentation of the PEARL project will be considered (list is not exhaustive):

- LOPE-C conference and fair – <https://www.lopec.com/en/>
- MRS - <https://www.mrs.org/meetings-events>
- EU-PVSEC - <https://www.eupvsec.org/>
- TechBlick - <https://www.techblick.com/>
- CES - <https://www.ces.tech/>
- PrintoCent Industry Seminar - <https://www.printocent.net/prinse>
- proflex - Roll-to-roll coating of flexible materials – conference series at Fraunhofer FEP - https://www.fep.fraunhofer.de/de/events/rueckblick_2021/proflex.html

Partners will provide updated information about events attendances in the 6-months internal report.

3.6.3. Technology news servers

Project will comply with knowledge sharing arrangement and will actively contribute to CORDIS – periodically, each time after the latest achievements, at least at the beginning and at the end of the project.

4. Conclusions

This strategy document is prepared in order to plan the best communication, and dissemination routes for the PEARL project results (e.g. through the project webpage, project dissemination materials, participation in events, etc.). Additional new routes will be investigated and if found relevant they will be integrated into the communication and dissemination road map.

When disseminating the results of the PEARL project, the following sentence will always be included as the acknowledgment of the EU funding: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101122283, project PEARL”.

5. Degree of progress

The deliverable is 100% fulfilled.

6. Dissemination level

The Deliverable 7.1 Dissemination and Communication is public and will therefore be available to download on the project's website.